

COMPUTER AIDED DESIGN IN FILAMENT WINDING OF STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Filament winding is widely used for manufacturing high quality composite structures, since it allows controlled continuous placement of the fibre with a high reproducible precision. Control of filament winding machine can be obtained using three or four axes of movements : the rotation of the mandrel, the two displacements of the feed-eye in a plane defined by the axis of rotation and the feed-eye and the rotation of the feed-eye about an horizontal axis perpendicular to the mandrel axis of rotation. Such a machine has the advantage of simplicity in operation and low cost compared to the five- or six-axis winding machines ; however, the control of the fibre placement is more difficult to obtain and still requires research work. The present paper is devoted to this study.

The first part of the work was to determine in a practical way the geodesic lines, considered as the stable fibre paths, for typical industrial structures. The end closures deserved special attention, particularly for the shapes not defined by analytical equations.

The second part analyses the control of the feed-eye position and rotation with respect to the rotation of the mandrel. The purpose was to optimize the feed-eye displacements taking into account technological constraints such as the overall dimensions of the structure to be manufactured and the travel of the feed-eye. Graphical simulation of the position and displacement is used to define the control parameters of the motion. Several examples of the feed-eye motion for winding simple and complex revolution shapes are presented.

INTRODUCTION

The use of fibre composites in highly-stressed mechanical components is of steadily increasing importance for design and production. In the case of revolution structures, such as shafts, wheel hubs, spindles and pressure vessels, the filament winding process is suitable to produce composites structures with high precision reproducible reinforcement.

To obtain an optimum filament winding process, from the point of view of time and cost of operation, four points must be considered: (1) definition of the geometry of the part to be wound in a practical way, (2) determination of the suitable stable path of the fibre on the mandrel, (3) determination of the feed-eye movements relative to the mandrel rotation, (4) connection between the previous points in a software able to transfer the computed data to the winding machine.

Since the beginning of the years 80, papers have been published about computerized winding machines^{1,2,3,4}, but few published work presents the automatization process. For example, the work of Shaw-Stewart⁵ presents the

software CADFIL which deals with axisymmetric parts only, the mandrel is simulated by pieces of cone or cylinder; this simulation leads to a non-negligible error in the fibre path, so that CADFIL fails to wind certain shapes with certain winding angles⁶ (fibre slip over the mandrel). The software CADMAC, presented by Wells & Eckold⁷, is based on the geometric definition of the part by 3-D modeller: the geodesic path is first determined, then the software simulates the winding process by defining successive straight lines tangential to the winding path at each point; the ends of these lines define, in the mandrel frame of reference, the successive locations of the feed-eye and the collision between the feed-eye and the mandrel should be checked for each position of the feed-eye. The possibility of winding on non-geodesic path is given in subsequent papers^{8,9}. The work of Kiberg & Menges¹⁰ presents a new method of simulation of filament winding process. The work of Léon¹¹ claims for a new approach dedicated to a computer aided manufacturing software for filament winding, based on a geometrical approach for the determination of the stable fibre path on general parts.

However, all the geometrical approaches in these papers simulate the surface by pieces of cone or cylinder⁵, by small square elements^{7,11} or by triangle plates inclined at angles to one another¹⁰. Further, they neglect some geometrical relations such as the exact formula for curvatures of the surface and the continuity between the different elements. So, though these approaches permit to deal with general shape in defining the geometry of the mandrel, they lead to an approximation, more or less accurate, in defining the stable path (geodesic or not). Further, when applied to parts with revolution symmetry, they consume large time in calculation that could be prevented by a separate algorithm specially designed for revolution surfaces.

In the present work, we introduce, for revolution parts, a new approach in surface simulation, then we determine with this surface description a stable winding path and the feed-eye position with respect to the mandrel rotation on three- or four-axis winding machines. The winding machine types concerned are described in the work of Abd El Hady & al.¹²

SIMULATION OF THE MERIDIONAL CURVE BY A GENERALIZED ELLIPTICAL EQUATION

The shape of the profile in most of the end domes of industrial revolution structures is usually designed from two circular segments (Fig. 1) or given point after point. For such domes, methods exist to determine the geodesic lines, which are convenient to manufacture mandrels. However, these methods are not suitable to perform the calculus of the differential geometry on the surfaces. Here we propose a new way to describe such domes by what we call a **general elliptical equation**, which has the following form :

$$\left(\frac{R_0}{R_c} \right)^m + \left(\frac{z}{b} \right)^n = 1 \quad (1)$$

With a convenient choice of the parameters m , n and b , we can simulate almost any open or closed dome. However some restrictions exist on the values of these parameters to insure the continuity of the tangent to the surface between the cylinder and the dome ($m > 1$), if this continuity is needed. In the following, we exemplify application of this method to simulate some domes:

1 - Domes given by two radii (Fig. 1)

We can distinguish four points 1, 2, 3 and 4 having respectively the following meridional radii : R_{01} , R_{02} , R_{03} and R_{04} with :

$$R_{01} = R_c, R_{02} = R_b \sin\phi_2, R_{03} = R_f \text{ and } R_{04} = 0$$

$$z_4 = b = R_b - (R_b - R_s) \cos\phi_2$$

By solving Eq. 1 for the last three points, we obtain the values of m , n and b ; with these values, Eq. 1 represents a general ellipse passing by the four points 1, 2, 3 and 4. The difference between real and simulated dome, in all cases was found to be negligible.

R_c : cylinder radius,
 R_f : end opening radius,
 R_b & R_s : dome radii.

Fig. 1 Geometry of a dome formed of two radii.

2 - Conical domes

To generate a conical shape from the general elliptical equation, we would have to impose: m and n equal to one, but it is preferable to choose for m a value strictly greater than one and very close to one (such as $m = 1.01$), which suppress the sharp angle at the connection between the cylinder and the dome. Further, taking for this example $b/R_c = 3$, and using Eq. 1 in calculating the geodesic path (Eq. 3), we get, for a winding angle of 10° , an angle θ at the opening equal to 249.15° , while the exact solution using the meridian equation of the cone gives a value of 252.98° , which gives an error less than 1.6 %.

So, we can conclude that this method is quite adapted and reveals very flexible and suitable to precise approximation. This method presented for end domes connected to cylinders can be extended to other connections.

DETERMINATION OF THE STABLE PATH OF THE FIBRE OVER A REVOLUTION SURFACE

In this part, we consider a geodesic line on the revolution surfaces as a stable path: as the geodesic line is the shortest distance between two points on the surface, it represents the position along which the placed fibre will not have tendency to slide over the surface. For revolution surfaces, the geodesic curve is defined by the Clairaut relationship, (Shilby¹³), according to Fig. 2 :

$$R_0 \sin \psi = \text{const.} \quad (2)$$

A study using some differential geometry of the surfaces was done in order to get the different parameters defining the surface and its tangential and normal vectors. From that study, the following relation is obtained (see Fig. 2):

$$d\theta = \frac{1}{R_0} \sqrt{\frac{(1+z^2)}{\left(\frac{R_0^2}{R_c^2 \sin^2 \psi_1} - 1\right)}} dR_0 \quad (3)$$

Integrating this equation gives the relation between θ and R_0 , which describes the geodesic curve on any revolution surface.

DETERMINATION OF THE FEED-EYE POSITION

In this part, we developed general relations relating the different feed-

eye movements, longitudinal and transversal to the mandrel rotation.

- G : geodesic curve,
- G_p : projection of the geodesic curve on the x-y plane,
- ψ : fibre angle,
- ψ₁ : winding angle on the cylindrical part,
- x₀ : position of the feed-eye in the x direction,
- z₀ : position of the feed-eye in the z direction,
- R₀(z) : meridian curve equation,
- r : position vector of the point M,
- EM : vector representing the fibre
- λ : fibre length,
- θ : position angle,
- z' : $\frac{dz}{dR_0}$

Fig. 2 General revolution surface.

By using the differential geometry of the surface, the feed-eye position is given by the following relations (according to Fig. 2) :

$$\tan \theta = \frac{\lambda \sin \psi}{\left(R_0 - \frac{\lambda R_0 \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R_0'^2}} \right)}$$

$$x_0 = R_0 - \frac{\lambda R_0 \cos \theta \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R_0'^2}} + \lambda \sin \theta \sin \psi \quad (4)$$

$$z_0 = \frac{\lambda \cos \psi}{\sqrt{1 + R_0'^2}} + z$$

Using these relations, we had chosen the following criterion of **winding with constant fibre length** (length of the fibre from the feed-eye to the surface of the mandrel) : this criterion is well suited to the cases of spherical domes and of conical and elliptical domes having a ratio of height to base radius greater than one.

Other winding criteria like winding with constant distance from the machine axis, which is well suited for cylinders or tubes with flat ends and elliptical ends with small ratio (less than one), and winding in a path parallel to the mandrel layout can also be chosen and are currently developed by the authors.

DETERMINATION OF THE FEED-EYE ROTATION

During the winding process, the fibres are drawn through the feed-eye, in form of a band-width a certain width (Fig. 3). In order to keep the band-width of the fibre over the mandrel constant and in the central part of the feed-eye, a rotation of the feed-eye must be introduced. This rotation is considered as the fourth axis of movement the winding machine possesses. In this movement, the feed-eye rotates about an horizontal axis perpendicular to the mandrel axis of rotation. This rotation is

given by the following relation :

$$\tan \phi = \frac{\cos \psi}{R_0 \sin \theta \sin \psi + \sqrt{1 + R_0^2 \cos \theta \sin \psi}} \quad (5)$$

The feed-eye rotation depends on other parameters, as the winding angle, the distance from the eye to the surface of the mandrel and the curvature of the surface.

Fig. 3 Delivering feed-eye shape.

DEVELOPMENT OF A WINDING SOFTWARE FOR REVOLUTION SURFACES

The equations of the previous analytical study were implemented in a numerical method. This method together with a numerical integration subroutine is used to form a complete software able to wind a great variety of combinations of revolution surfaces. The advantage of our software over other existing softwares is its simplicity in entering the surface geometry, its rapidity in the calculation and its ability to wind a large number of combinations of revolution surfaces at almost all angles. Another great advantage of this software lies on the graphical representation of the layout of the mandrel with respect to the feed-eye motion and of the total required distance that the feed-eye needs longitudinally and transversally. So the operator can adjust his initial machine setting to be in the allowable range of the machine and to permit winding without collision. An example of the graphical output of the software is shown in Fig. 4. In the given example, the following notations are used :

- a_1 : winding angle at the beginning of the conical part (left side),
- a_2 : winding angle at the end of the conical part,
- d_1 : winding angle over the left dome,
- d_2 : winding angle over the right dome,

The points 1, 2, 3, etc .. on the figures indicate the points on the mandrel and their similar on the feed-eye path, and the symbol 'o' indicates the connections of different parts where the tangent continuity is not imposed.

Fig. 4 Feed-eye path for winding a combination of two spherical domes connected by a cone and two cylinders ($a_1 = 30^\circ$, $a_2 = 41.81^\circ$, $d_1 = 30^\circ$, $d_2 = 33.75^\circ$).

An extension of the present study, concerning winding on non-geodesic path, based on the friction between the surface and the fibre, the normal curvature and the differential geometry of the part have been done and a routine which incorporates the corresponding formulas has been integrated within the software. Given a certain winding angle and shape of mandrel, the software checked the possibility of winding on a geodesic path; if not, it defines a stable non-geodesic path. Fig. 4 show an example in winding on non-geodesic path, which leads to different values for a_2 and d_2 .

CONCLUSION

In the present work, we gave a complete study for the surface simulation of different revolution shapes, the geodesic path on these surface as well as the feed-eye position and rotation with respect to the mandrel rotation. The simulation of the surface of the part by a general elliptical equation is quite adapted and reveals very flexible and suitable to precise approximation. A computer-aided design software has been developed and implemented in industrial winding machine (Berthiez Productics). In addition to its simplicity in entering the data and its rapidity in calculation the software has proved a very high efficiency in winding different combined revolution shapes and sizes of mandrel at different angles. The graphical representation of the mandrel and the feed-eye movement permit the operator to adjust the initial machine setting to prevent collision between the feed-eye and the mandrel.

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